

Supplementary Material

Obesity and Pregnancy: Maternal and Neonatal Complications

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Introduction

Maternal obesity is a well-established risk factor for adverse outcomes in both mother and child. Achieving appropriate gestational weight gain through balanced nutrition and regular moderate-intensity physical activity can reduce the likelihood of pregnancy complications and long-term health consequences. Women who enter pregnancy overweight or obese are at increased risk for conditions such as gestational diabetes, hypertensive disorders, and delivery complications, which may also affect neonatal health. Adopting a healthy diet and engaging in safe, moderate exercise before conception and throughout pregnancy support normal weight gain and mitigate these risks. Furthermore, fostering a supportive family and social environment is essential to encourage and sustain these health-promoting behaviors, ultimately safeguarding the well-being of both mother and infant.

Aim

The purpose of this review is to highlight and examine the association between maternal obesity and its consequences for both mother and newborn, providing insight for individuals planning pregnancy. This review aims to identify lifestyle practices and interventions that can reduce the risk of obesity-related adverse health outcomes for mothers and infants. In addition, it explores the barriers women face and the motivations that influence their adoption of healthy behaviors.

Materials and Methods

This study presents a systematic review of the literature, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative evidence, including randomized controlled trials and observational studies published between 2019 and 2024. The literature search was performed in the PubMed and Google Scholar databases and was restricted to open-access publications.

Keywords: women, factors, weight, pregnancy, complications, obesity

Results:

The findings showed serious effects of obesity in pregnancy such as hypertension which can lead to pre-eclampsia, gestational diabetes mellitus, increased caesarean section and maternal mortality after delivery, increased biochemical markers in early pregnancy, mental health issues, other problems such as infertility and fertility. Also large for gestational age babies, low Apgar score, increased risk of neonatal mortality and childhood obesity later. It turns out that the various dietary patterns such as the Western, the Mediterranean, the vegetarian pattern or the dietary pattern of high-quality proteins have effects on gestational weight, affect the health of the mother, are related, like malnutrition, to other social characteristics of women, (Table 1).

Table 1. Maternal Obesity in Pregnancy — Summary of Main Findings

Obstetric and Neonatal Complications	Studies	Results
Maternal metabolic & obstetric complications	Leblanc et al. 2021; Akselsson et al. 2021; Saucedo et al. 2021; Bone et al. 2023;	Higher BMI before or during pregnancy increases risk of gestational diabetes, hypertension, preeclampsia, caesarean delivery, maternal mortality and longer hospital stay.
Mental health & fertility	Van Uytsel et al. 2023; Bloon et al. 2020; Legro et al. 2022; Svensson et al. 2022	Obesity linked to postpartum anxiety and depression, anovulation, reduced fertility and IVF success; lifestyle interventions improve weight but not always pregnancy rates.
Diet & weight gain	Zhang et al. 2024; Chen & Harrison 2022; Xing Yu. Et al. 2020; Santos et al. 2022; Janumala et al. 2020	Pre-pregnancy BMI predicts diet quality and gestational weight gain; low-intensity lifestyle programs help control weight and postpartum retention; exercise and counseling may improve outcomes.
Neonatal & long-term child outcomes	Huvinen et al. 2021; Josey et al. 2019; Chen et al. 2021	Maternal obesity associated with large-for-gestational-age infants, neonatal mortality, later childhood obesity and increased child adiposity at age 5.
Socioeconomic & care barriers	Vander et al. 2019; Grenier et al. 2022; Goldstein et al. 2020	Low income and education linked to obesity and poor diet; unclear guidelines, limited knowledge and weak

		professional support hinder healthy habits and weight control in pregnancy.
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Conclusions:

Although most women are aware of the consequences of being overweight during pregnancy—both for themselves and for the newborn—and wish to achieve a healthy weight by adopting healthy behaviors, they face significant barriers that hinder this goal. Substantial action from the government and public health authorities is needed to promote a healthy profile before pregnancy, during gestation, and after childbirth.

Abbreviation

Abbreviation	Full Term
BMI	Body Mass Index
IVF	In Vitro Fertilization

References

- Akselsson A, Rossen J, Storck-Lindholm E, Rådestad I. Prolonged pregnancy and stillbirth among women with overweight or obesity - a population-based study in Sweden including 64,632 women. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2023 Jan 12;23(1):21, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-022-05340-4>
- Bloom M, Perkins N, Sjaarda L, et al: Adiposity is associated with anovulation independent of serum free testosterone: A prospective cohort study. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*, 2020, 35(2): 174-184, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppe.12726>
- Bone MSc J, PhD Joseph K, Magee MD L, et al. Pre-pregnancy body mass index and adverse perinatal outcomes in the presence of other maternal risk factors. *AJOC Global Reports*, 2023 Feb 8;3(2):100175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xagr.2023.100175>
- Chen M, Lim S, Harrison C: Limiting Postpartum Weight Retention in Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Women: Secondary Analysis of the HeLP-her Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nutrients*, 2022 Jul 21;14(14):2988, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14142988>
- Chen Yu , Zhang T, Chen C et al. Associations of early pregnancy BMI with adverse pregnancy outcomes and infant neurocognitive development. *Sci Rep*. 2021 Feb 15;11(1):3793, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-83430-7>
- Huvinen E, Tuomaala AK, Bergman P . Ascending Growth is Associated with Offspring Adiposity in Pregnancies Complicated with Obesity or Gestational Diabetes. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2021, Apr 23;106(5):e1993-e2004, <https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgaa979>
- Janumala Isaiah, Toro-Ramos Tatiana, Widen Elizabeth, et al: Increased Visceral Adipose Tissue Without Weight Retention at 59 Weeks Postpartum. *Obesity(Silver Spring)*, 2020 Mar;28(3):552-562, <https://doi.org/10.1002/oby.22736>
- Josey Michele J, McCullough Lauren E, Hoyo Cathrine et al. Overall gestational weight gain mediates the relationship between maternal and child obesity. *BMC Public Health*, 2019 Aug 7;19(1):1062, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7349-1>
- Goldstein Rebecca F, Boyle Jacqueline A, Lo Clement, et al. Facilitators and barriers to behavior change within a lifestyle program for women with obesity to prevent excess gestational weight gain: a mixed methods evaluation. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2021, Aug 18;21(1):569, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-021-04034-7>

Grenier L, Atkinson S, Mottola M, et al. Be Healthy in Pregnancy: Exploring factors that impact pregnant women nutrition and exercise behaviours. *Matern Child Nutr*, 2021 Jan;17(1):e13068, <https://doi.org/10.1111/mcn.13068>

Leblanc Erin S, Smith, Ning X, Vesco Kimberly k, Hillier Teresa A, Stevens Victor J. Weight Loss Prior to Pregnancy and Early Gestational Glycemia: Prepare, a Randomized Clinical Trial. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 106 (12) 2021 Jul 27;106(12):e5001–e5010. doi: [10.1210/clinem/dgab547](https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgab547)

Legro R, Hansen K, Diamond M, et al. Effects of preconception life style intervention in infertile women with obesity: The FIT-PLESE randomized controlled trial. *JOURNAL PLOS MEDICINE*: 2022, Jan 18;19(1):e1003883, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1003883>

Santos K, Rosado E, Proenca da Fonseca, et al. FTO and ADRB2 Genetic Polymorphisms Are Risk Factors for Earlier Excessive Gestational Weight Gain in Pregnant Women with Pregestational Diabetes Mellitus: Results of a Randomized Nutrigenetic Trial. *Nutrients*, 2022 Mar 1;14(5):1050, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14051050>

Saucedo M, Esteve-Pereira A, Pencole L, et al. Understanding maternal mortality in women with obesity and the role of care they receive: a national case-control study. *International Journal of Obesity*, 2021 Jan;45(1):258-265. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41366-020-00691-4>

Svensson H, Einarsson S, Olausson D, Kluge L, Bergh C, Edén S, Lönn M, Thurin-Kjellberg A. Inflammatory and metabolic markers in relation to outcome of in vitro fertilization in a cohort of predominantly overweight and obese women. *Sci Rep*. 2022 Aug 3;12(1):13331, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-17612-2>

Van Uytsel H, Ameye L, Devlieger R, Jacquemyn Y et al. Mental Health during the Interpregnancy Period and the Association with Pre-Pregnancy Body Mass Index and Body Composition: Data From the INTER-ACT Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nutrients*, 2023 Jul 14;15(14):3152, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15143152>

Vander Wyst Kiley B, Quintana Guadalupe, Balducci James. et al. Comparison and Characterization of Prenatal Nutrition Counseling among Large-for-Gestational Age Deliveries by Pre-Pregnancy BMI. *Nutrients* 2019, 11(12), 3018, <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11123018>

Xing Yu, Wang Xin, Zhang Weiyuan et al. The effect of exercise on maternal complications and birth outcomes in overweight or obese pregnant women: a meta-analysis. *ANNALS OF PALLIATIVE MEDICINE*, 2020 Nov;9(6):4103-4112, <https://doi.org/10.21037/apm-20-2097>

Zhang Juan, Wang Xue, Zhu Ping: Exploring the relationships between pre-pregnancy BMI, gestational weight gain, and nutritional intake: a real- world investigation in Shandong, China. *Peer J*: 2024 Mar 22;12:e17099, <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.17099>